

Rac-5i

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-103-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	20	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 103 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/9/2022 9:18:51 AM CST		
Date Processed:	4/10/2022 4:38:43 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.817	12554513	50.59	380660
2	16.139	12261048	49.41	339875

Asy-5i

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-103-asy-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	32	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 103 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/9/2022 9:45:35 AM CST		
Date Processed:	4/10/2022 4:36:29 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	14.718	315019	3.61	9543
2	15.969	8418233	96.39	241341